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Corrosion Models, Diagnosis and Prognosis in Offshore Wind Turbine Towers

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Motivation

- Offshore wind turbines are located increasingly further from the shore.
- Regular manual inspections are becoming increasingly costly.

Remote and continuous diagnosis and prognosis of offshore wind turbines

Reduction in operational expenditure (OPEX)

- Monitoring using ultrasound sensors: noninvasive, accurate, and relatively inexpensive.

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Little historical data

Bimodal corrosion model: 4 phases suitable for wet conditions, including wind turbine splash zone

[Melchers, 2003]

Corrosion simulation tool based on bimodal corrosion model

$ir_0 = 0.07 \text{ mm/yr}$, $linEnd = 1.21 \text{ yr}$, $ta_1 = 3.60 \text{ yr}$, $ca_1 = 0.06 \text{ mm}$, $tM_2 = 4.81 \text{ yr}$
 $ir_0 = 0.08 \text{ mm/yr}$, $ta_2 = 9.49 \text{ yr}$, $ca_2 = 0.23 \text{ mm}$ ($B=0.024$), $tLin = 9.49 \text{ yr}$

Simulated corrosion measurement data

Simulation of ground truth:

- We use the bimodal model of [Melchers, 2003] together with the provided real-life values for the constants.
- The remaining unknown constants were fitted against plots of historical corrosion data by using the simulation tool.
- Seasonal temperature effect is introduced by adding the factor

$$e^{T-T_{ref}}$$

to the corrosion rate.

Simulation of measurement data:

- For ultrasound sensors, a Gaussian measurement uncertainty of 5 μm is typical and used to simulate the measurement data.

Prognosis pipeline

Two algorithms based on two degradation models:

(1) Constant corrosion rate

(2) Bimodal model

Prognosis based on constant corrosion rate

- Idea: assume constant corrosion rate and let measurements adapt to this corrosion rate.
- State-transition and measurement functions are linear, measurement noise is Gaussian, and process noise is assumed Gaussian → Kalman filtering is applicable, fast, and optimal.
- Drawback: degradation model corresponds to reality only in first and last corrosion phases.

Prognosis based on bimodal model

- Idea: let Bayesian filtering “learn” not only suitable parameters for each of the 4 phases, but also the phase transition times.
- State-transition is very non-linear, so Kalman filtering is not suitable. Extended Kalman filtering and Unscented Kalman filtering are suitable → Unscented Kalman filtering is chosen as: accuracy is more important than speed since corrosion is a slow process.
- Drawback: complex model with many (9) parameters to learn → high burden on Bayesian filtering and risk of fitting the parameters to unrealistic values.

Results

Constant rate

Bimodal model

wall thickness estimation

corrosion rate estimation

RUL estimation

Conclusions

- Generated simulated corrosion measurement data for the splash zone of a wind turbine.
- Evaluated the performance of two corrosion prognosis algorithms that use Bayesian filtering techniques.
- Accuracy of the RUL estimates of both algorithms are high at the (most important) latter half of the wall structure lifetime.
- Bimodal prognosis algorithm has a better RUL estimate in the first half of the wall lifetime compared to the constant-rate algorithm.
- However, constant-rate prognosis algorithm will likely provide more robust results in the case of (very) low quality measurement data.

Future work

- Focus on degradation models ``in between'' the constant-rate corrosion model (having 1 constant) and the 9-constant bimodal model.
- Consider degradation models where temperature is included explicitly.
- Validate the developed prognostics framework on experimental data obtained from accelerated corrosion tests that are currently being performed.

End

Thanks!